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Eardrum sound pressure prediction from ear canal reflectance based on the inverse solution of Webster's horn equation

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ABSTRACT:

To derive ear canal transfer functions for individualized equalization algorithms of in-ear hearing systems, individual ear canal models are needed. In a one-dimensional approach, this requires the estimation of the individual area function of the ear canal. The area function can be effectively and reproducibly calculated as the inverse solution of Webster's horn equation by finite difference approximation of the time domain reflectance. Building upon previous research, the present study further investigates the termination of the approximation at an optimal spatial resolution, addressing the absence of higher frequencies in typical ear canal measurements and enhancing the accuracy of the inverse solution. Compared to the geometric reference, more precise area functions were achieved by extrapolating simulated input impedances of ear canal geometries up to a frequency of 3.5 MHz, corresponding to 0.1 mm spatial resolution. The low pass of the previous work was adopted but adjusted for its cutoff frequency, depending on the highest frequency of the band limited input impedance. Robust criteria for terminating the area function at the approximated ear canal length were found. Finally, three-dimensional simulated and measured ear canal transfer impedances were replicated well, employing the previously introduced and herein validated one-dimensional electro-acoustic model fed by the area functions.

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I. INTRODUCTION

Acoustic transparency is often desired to improve the sound quality of in-ear hearing systems. Transparency means that the device adjusts the sound pressure at the eardrum so that the user experiences a natural, open sound while wearing the hearing device. To achieve this, the sound pressure at the eardrum with and without the hearing device must be known, ideally for each individual. The first step is to determine the transfer function of the individual ear canal when the device is in use, which is the focus of the present study. To this end, a hearing system equipped with a microphone placed at the residual ear canal can be employed as an impedance probe to derive the input impedance of the residual ear canal from a short measurement (Sankowsky-Rothe *et al.*, 2011; Vogl and Blau, 2019). The ear canal input impedance provides sufficient information to potentially assess the sound pressure at the eardrum. There are various methods to predict sound pressure at the eardrum, but many of them (Lewis and Neely, 2015; Vogl and Blau, 2019; Wulbusch *et al.*, 2023) involve complex fitting processes and associated challenges, including high

computational demands, the need for carefully selecting fitting parameters (e.g., the number of iterations, error tolerances, initial values, and constraints) or convergence problems due to local minima of the error function. Some may also require additional knowledge, such as the approximate ear canal length in order to constrain the parameter space.

Hence, a single concise calculation like the inverse solution of Webster's horn equation using a finite difference approximation from time domain reflectance (TDR), as proposed by Rasetshwane and Neely (2011), with a subsequent one-dimensional transfer model would be preferable. However, as will be shown below, the original method in Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) unfortunately underestimates area functions, which means that the predicted sound pressure at the eardrum may be inaccurate.

Considering the analytical case of an exponential horn, a parabolic horn, and a conical horn with known monotonically growing shapes, the method in Rasetshwane *et al.* (2012) differs from that in Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) in that the spatial resolution is much higher and the number of iterations limiting the finite difference approximation is given by the known length of the horn. Inverse solutions were shown to agree very well with the theoretical ones, but real ear canals may pose additional challenges. Related literature mainly

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refers to the problem of a non-causal TDR due to neglecting wavefront curvature and evanescent modes for non-uniform ear canals (Nørgaard *et al.*, 2019; Keefe, 2020). Apart from these concerns, a consistent investigation concerning the dependence of prediction accuracy on selected parameters of the method would be a useful supplement. Furthermore, to the best of our knowledge, there is currently no validation comparing the derived area functions of individual ear canals with a known reference from three-dimensional scans nor regarding resulting eardrum pressure predictions.

The present study aims to modify the method by Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) while retaining the model assumptions to further enhance the prediction accuracy of the area function of individual ear canals and the eardrum sound pressure. The paper is organized as follows: Sec. II provides a comprehensive overview of the theoretical foundations that have been established in previous studies, needed to calculate the drum pressure using the inverse solution of Webster’s horn equation by a finite difference approximation. The methods employed in the present study are delineated in Sec. III, which is further subdivided into two parts. First, the reference data on acoustic transmission in ear canals are introduced. The second part contains the procedure and methodological modifications to previous work for the best possible estimation of the sound pressure at the eardrum. In Sec. IV, the dependence of the prediction accuracy on selected parameters is investigated by comparing the estimate of the ear canal transfer impedance to three-dimensional finite element method (FEM) simulations. After selecting the best parameters, the optimized method is validated on the basis of measurements. This is followed by the discussion and conclusion in Secs. V and VI.

II. DRUM PRESSURE CALCULATION VIA INVERSE SOLUTION OF WEBSTER’S HORN EQUATION

A. Reflectance at the entrance of horns

The input impedance at the lateral end of an ear canal, $Z_{ec}(\omega)$, with the angular frequency ω , can be determined by measuring the sound pressure at the lateral end with known source parameters and microphone characteristics (Keefe *et al.*, 1992; Voss and Allen, 1994; Blau *et al.*, 2010; Sankowsky-Rothe *et al.*, 2011; Sankowsky-Rothe *et al.*, 2012; Sankowsky-Rothe *et al.*, 2015; Vogl and Blau, 2019; Rasetshwane and Neely, 2011). The frequency domain reflectance $R(x, \omega)$ at the lateral end $x = 0$, with x giving the center axis position, results from the input impedance Z_{ec} and the characteristic impedance Z_0 at $x = 0$,

$$R(x = 0, \omega) = \frac{Z_{ec}(\omega) - Z_0(x = 0)}{Z_{ec}(\omega) + Z_0(x = 0)}. \quad (1)$$

In general, Z_0 is the ratio of the fluid density ρ times the speed of sound c and the area function A ,

$$Z_0(x = 0) = \frac{\rho c}{A(x = 0)}, \quad (2)$$

which implies that the area function at $x = 0$ must be known. Here, we follow the iterative procedure for estimating the characteristic impedance $Z_0(x = 0)$ in Rasetshwane and Neely (2011), by using MATLAB scripts provided in Rasetshwane (2012a) for measurements on unknown ear canals. The steps of this procedure are outlined in Sec. II C. It should be added that Eq. (2) only applies to ideal acoustic systems with a purely real-valued characteristic impedance Z_0 without dispersion or any damping. In real systems like ear canals, it may also contain an uncertain and presumably negligible imaginary part describing losses and phase shifts [see, e.g., Kuttruff (2007), p. 155, regarding dispersion in exponential horns].

B. Inverse solution of Webster’s horn equation

Webster’s horn equation was derived for semi-infinite and rigidly bounded horns with slowly varying area functions, for frequencies with large wavelengths compared to the transversal horn dimension to ensure one-dimensional propagation (Webster, 1919). Applications often address horns of monotonically growing area functions as in the phonograph or acoustic loudspeakers (Goldsmith and Minton, 1924). The equation can also be applied to horn structures in microphones to optimize acoustic performance and enhance frequency response, to horn channels in hearing aids, to horn-shaped structures in auditory spaces or concert halls, in musical instruments such as trumpets, or in acoustic sensors.

Following the notation in Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) and Rasetshwane *et al.* (2012), Webster’s horn equation is given by

$$\partial_x p(x, t) = -\frac{\rho}{A(x)} \partial_t u(x, t) \quad (3)$$

and

$$\partial_x u(x, t) = -\frac{A(x)}{\rho c^2} \partial_t^2 p(x, t), \quad (4)$$

where $p(x, t)$ is the sum of the superimposed incoming $p_+(x, t)$ and outgoing wave $p_-(x, t)$,

$$p(x, t) = p_+(x, t) + p_-(x, t). \quad (5)$$

The TDR $r(x, t)$ is defined as the deconvolution of $p_-(x, t)$ by $p_+(x, t)$. It is assumed to be zero for $t < 0$ for all values of x , ensuring causality. Eliminating the volume velocity $u(x, t)$ in Eqs. (3) and (4) results in an equation of second order,

$$\partial_x^2 p(x, t) + 2\epsilon(x) \partial_x p(x, t) - \frac{1}{c^2} \partial_t^2 p(x, t) = 0, \quad (6)$$

with

$$\epsilon(x) \equiv \frac{1}{2} \frac{d}{dx} \ln A(x). \quad (7)$$

The entire procedure for solving Webster’s horn equation for $A(x)$ by finite difference approximation is described by Rasetshwane *et al.* (2012), and a MATLAB implementation was provided in Rasetshwane (2012a) and Rasetshwane (2012b).

By means of the inverse Fourier transform of $R(x, \omega)$, the TDR $r(x, t)$ is obtained. In discrete time, the temporal resolution Δt of $r(x, t)$ must be chosen small enough to satisfy the stability criterion, according to Courant *et al.* (1928). Here, this is ensured by linking Δt to the highest frequency f_{sup} with $\Delta t = 1/f_{sup}$.

C. Previous work

For the present study, there are two previous publications regarding the inverse solution. The first article (Rasetshwane and Neely, 2011) is dedicated to the inverse solution of Webster’s horn equation using a finite difference approximation to TDR, for measurements with a fixed sampling rate of $f_s = 48$ kHz on human ear canals. The authors used upsampling at rates up to 192 kHz, by zero-padding the frequency domain reflectance. The upsampling rates f_{sup} were obtained from integer multiples n_{sup} of the sampling rate f_s . They also used an amplitude correction by multiplying the frequency domain reflectance with n_{sup} , as found in the earlier version of the supplementary material of Rasetshwane (2012a). This correction is no longer found in the later version (Rasetshwane, 2012b). A frequency domain Blackman window, $W(\aleph)$, given by

$$W(\aleph) = \begin{cases} \frac{1 - a + \cos(\aleph) + a \cdot \cos(2 \cdot \aleph)}{2} & \text{if } 0 \leq \aleph \leq \pi \\ 0 & \text{if } \aleph > \pi \end{cases} \tag{8}$$

for

$$\aleph = \frac{\pi \cdot n \cdot f_{sup}}{N \cdot f_{cut}}, \tag{9}$$

with $a = 0.16$ and $n = 0, 1, \dots, N/2$, where N is the fast Fourier transform (FFT) length, was used on the upsampled frequency domain reflectance [conforming with Rasetshwane (2012a) and Rasetshwane (2012b)]. This window increasingly attenuated levels at higher frequencies and suppressed them completely from f_{cut} onwards, by setting $W(\aleph > \pi) = 0$. Figure 1 shows this frequency domain window, together with all other specific frequencies of the algorithm: f_{lim} defines the highest frequency for which a value for the input impedance or reflectance is available. In Rasetshwane and Neely (2011), f_{lim} was set to the Nyquist frequency $f_s/2$ and f_{cut} was smaller than f_{lim} .

Last, the TDR for $t > 0$ was reversed in time and added with the reflectance for $t > 0$ (time-reversed addition), eliminating a signal-processing artifact not reported in detail. This step has disappeared in Rasetshwane (2012b).

As previously mentioned in Sec. II A, Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) adjusted Z_0 by an iterative procedure, reducing the TDR at $t = 0$, which unfortunately was not explained in more detail. The supplementary material in Rasetshwane (2012a) contains the source code for the aforementioned process, henceforth referred to as “surge I.” In the first step, an initial estimate of $Z_0(x = 0)$ is calculated. In the second step, the frequency domain reflectance $R(x = 0, \omega)$ is calculated, using the current estimate of Z_0 , where the frequency domain Blackman window is used to eliminate ringing in the TDR. Third, the mean real part of the current windowed $R(x = 0, \omega)$, denoted by $m_{R,k}$, is divided by the mean of the window function, m_W , and $Z_{0,k}$ is iteratively updated via

$$Z_{0,k+1} = Z_{0,k} \cdot \left(1 + \frac{m_{R,k}}{m_W} \right). \tag{10}$$

Steps 2 and 3 are repeated until the value of $Z_0(x = 0)$ converges to a single value.

A modified variant adjusting the characteristic impedance can be found in Rasetshwane (2012b), henceforth referred to as “surge II.” In this approach, $R(x = 0, \omega)$ was not calculated with the real-valued $Z_0(x = 0)$, as in Eq. (1), but rather with a complex-valued characteristic impedance.

Subsequent to the calculation of $Z_0(x = 0)$ and $R(x = 0, \omega)$, the inverse solution can be calculated. Since the correct length of the ear canal is not known initially, considerations for abort criteria or constraints for the finite difference approximation are needed. First, Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) set a maximum length, l_{max} , which was assumed to be larger than the expected geometric length, l_{geoend} , of the unknown ear canal or simulator. Subsequently, the TDR peak latency was associated with the length l_{TDRmax} at the point of reflection at the eardrum. Furthermore, it was assumed in Rasetshwane (2012b) that the possible end of the entire ear canal is at length l_{TDR50} , where the TDR has decayed to 50% after reaching its maximum.

Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) mentioned to validate their method by the use of an ear canal simulator consisting of 15 brass tubes connected to each other with a rigid termination. The best match occurred for an upsampling factor n_s of 4 at a sampling rate of 48 kHz with $f_{cut} = 17$ kHz [see Fig. 2 in Rasetshwane and Neely (2011)].

FIG. 1. Blackman window, as designed by Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) and also found in Rasetshwane (2012b), and characteristic frequencies.

In addition, the spatial resolution Δx is quite coarse with ≈ 1.8 mm for $f_{\text{sup}} = 4 \cdot 48$ kHz. In contrast, a spatial resolution of the ear canal of at least 1 mm is recommended by [Hudde et al. \(1999\)](#) and even 0.1 mm by [Xia et al. \(2024\)](#). Thus, there are four parameters in the work of [Rasetshwane and Neely \(2011\)](#), namely, $f_{\text{lim}} = f_s/2, f_{\text{cut}}, f_{\text{sup}}$, and the length l terminating the ear canal, that need to be considered in more detail. A consistent exploration of the dependency of the resulting Z_{trans} on selected parameters is therefore undertaken in the present work.

For geometries as analyzed in the second article ([Rasetshwane et al., 2012](#)), the impedance or reflectance can also be analytically determined. Authors considered simply shaped exponential, conical, and parabolic horns with known monotonically growing area functions and *a priori* known lengths. In [Rasetshwane et al. \(2012\)](#), the method from [Rasetshwane and Neely \(2011\)](#) was used, but the chosen sampling rate of 1 MHz with accompanying spatial resolution $\Delta x \approx 0.35$ mm made upsampling and low-pass filtering unnecessary. Equation (2) with the known $A(x=0)$ was employed to calculate $Z_0(x=0)$ without any adjustment. The inverse solution resulted in quite accurate area functions compared to the known reference with diameter deviations less than 4%. As discussed by the authors, the remaining errors might be caused by the violated assumption of one-dimensional wave propagation for smaller wavelengths and the incorrect assumption for the characteristic impedance, especially for parabolic horns. Furthermore, authors reported that errors systematically increase for smaller sampling rates, which also addresses the issue of band limited measurements on ear canals.

D. One-dimensional electro-acoustic (EA) model

The estimated area function given by the inverse solution of Webster’s horn equation is only an intermediate step. In order to compute the eardrum sound pressure, p_d , a one-dimensional approach via two-port models comprising a source model, a transmission model, and a load model as introduced by [Sankowsky-Rothe et al. \(2015\)](#) is used in the present study. The circuit diagram of this EA model is shown in Fig. 2. The transmission matrix of the ear canal, whose parameters e_{ij} are determined by the area function, results from a chain of single tube segments, each modeled

as a lossless acoustic duct, according to [Benade \(1968\)](#). The load Z_l represents the eardrum acoustic impedance acting in parallel to the acoustic impedance of the residual volume medial to the umbo point projected on the centerline (CL), according to [Hudde and Engel \(1998\)](#). The shunt impedance Z_e represents the residual error between the measured and modeled Z_{ec} and compensates for additional leakage, unmodeled attenuation and the individual mismatch between the true and generalized non-individual eardrum impedance.

Since the (known) input impedance Z_{ec} already contains information on the attenuation by thermo-viscous effects, skin, and leakage, one can derive an expression for the transfer impedance Z_{trans} without explicit reference to Z_l and Z_e . Using the circuit diagram from Fig. 2, one obtains

$$\begin{bmatrix} p_{\text{ec}} \\ q_{\text{ec}} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ \frac{1}{Z_e} & 1 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} e_{11} & e_{12} \\ e_{21} & e_{22} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} p_d \\ q_d \end{bmatrix} = \mathbf{B} \begin{bmatrix} p_d \\ q_d \end{bmatrix} \quad (11)$$

as the relationship between sound pressure and volume velocity at the lateral end of the ear canal, p_{ec} and q_{ec} , and the sound pressure and volume velocity at the eardrum, p_d and q_d . Noting that

$$Z_{\text{ec}} = \frac{p_{\text{ec}}}{q_{\text{ec}}}, \quad (12)$$

$$Z_{\text{trans}} = \frac{p_d}{q_{\text{ec}}}, \quad (13)$$

it follows through the inverse matrix \mathbf{B}^{-1} , whereas, $\det(\mathbf{B}) = 1$ according to the reciprocity principle for passive linear systems ([Strutt, 1871](#)), that

$$Z_{\text{trans}} = e_{22}Z_{\text{ec}} - e_{12} + \frac{e_{12}Z_{\text{ec}}}{Z_e}. \quad (14)$$

[Sankowsky-Rothe et al. \(2015\)](#) suggested neglecting the third term in Eq. (14), as it is considered to be small. More specifically, Z_e is a mainly mass-dominated impedance with low level at low frequencies and increasing level towards high frequencies. Depending on the size of the leakage, the levels of Z_e and Z_{ec} cross—at a frequency that is typically below 1 kHz for smaller leakage due to venting or a slightly leaky fit of the ear mold. Hence, the third term becomes very small above 1 kHz. At lower frequencies, it can be safely assumed that e_{12} is very low since, in acoustically short waveguides, it is approximately proportional to the ratio of the ear canal length to the wavelength. Thus, as given in [Sankowsky-Rothe et al. \(2015\)](#), the transfer impedance is merely an expression of only two transfer parameters of the ear canal and the measured input impedance,

$$Z_{\text{trans}} \approx e_{22}Z_{\text{ec}} - e_{12}. \quad (15)$$

Finally, if q_{ec} is computed using the in-ear-hearing device as probe to determine Z_{ec} ([Blau et al., 2010](#); [Sankowsky-Rothe et al., 2015](#); [Vogl and Blau, 2019](#)), the sound pressure at the eardrum p_d can be derived from Z_{trans} in Eq. (13). Errors in

FIG. 2. One-dimensional electro-acoustic model used to calculate the transfer impedance Z_{trans} from the input impedance Z_{ec} of the ear canal (defined as ratios of the drum pressure p_d or the pressure at the lateral end of the ear canal p_{ec} to the volume velocity at the lateral end of the ear canal q_{ec} [Eqs. (12) and (13)].

the prediction of Z_{trans} thus also result in errors on the predicted p_d . In the following, the transfer impedance Z_{trans} is considered.

III. METHODS

A. Reference data on acoustic transmission in ear canals

1. Geometrically determined area functions of ear canals

The IHA database of individual three-dimensional geometries consisting of torso, head, and complete outer ears, including the ear canals with eardrums [see Roden and Blau (2020); published in Roden and Blau (2025)], is being used in the present study. More specifically, the geometries of the right ear canal of subjects 1–21 in the IHA database were used. First, the ear canals (and parts of the concha) were extracted from the stl files in the database. The CL of each ear canal between a point lateral to the ear canal entrance and the innermost corner of the ear canal was then determined utilizing the vmtk toolbox (Antiga, 2002). CLs were also determined according to Stinson and Lawton (1989). Both methods resulted in similar CLs, except for strongly curved ear canals, where the vmtk method appeared to better follow the shape of the ear canals. (A detailed comparison is beyond the scope of the present article.) In the following, CLs extracted with the vmtk toolbox are used for the geometric analysis.

The entrance of the ear canal was defined as the first plane (seen from the lateral side) orthogonal to the CL, which intersected the ear canal walls to form a closed ring of polygon vertices, as proposed by Balouch et al. (2023). The first and second bends were initially determined by visual inspection. The nearest local torsion or curvature maximum of the CL was then used to determine the first and second bends on the CL in a reproducible manner. For computations with ear canals of different lengths, the ear canals were sectioned by planes orthogonal to the CL at the entrance and at the first and second bends. Figure 3 shows an example of ear canal geometry with CL and landmarks

FIG. 3. Right outer ear of subject 3 in the IHA database, with the extracted centerline and landmarks (left) and with final cut planes at the entrance, the first and second bends, and at the eardrum (right).

(left) and a pinna with resulting cut planes (right). The areas of the orthogonal cross-sections along the CL result in area functions shown in Fig. 4 for the right ear canals of subjects 1–21 of the IHA database (cut at the entrance), as well as for ear canals from various other studies.

The surface of the tympanic membrane was identified by geometric estimation of its approximate rim. For this purpose, the cross-sectional polygons of the medial end of the ear canal were interpolated and the points with the maximum curvature in the region of the rim were extracted. The plane with the smallest Euclidian distance from these points was defined as the cut plane to separate the ear canal walls and eardrum. The umbo point was identified as the highest elevation of the tympanic membrane above the cut plane.

2. Three-dimensional FEM simulations of input and transfer impedances

a. Simulations using human ear canal geometries. In order to analyze the input and transfer impedance of ear canals, three-dimensional FEM simulations were carried out utilizing COMSOL MULTIPHYSICS 6.2 (COMSOL AB, Stockholm, Sweden) in a similar way to that described in Roden and Blau (2020) and Wulbusch et al. (2023). The impedance according to Hudde and Engel (1998) for the tympanic membrane and medial structures was assigned to the eardrum surface.

As suggested by Berggren et al. (2018) and Bach and Bruus (2018), the thermo-viscous effects in the immediate vicinity of the ear canal walls were described by a boundary layer impedance (BLI) as a weak contribution to the Helmholtz equation. Furthermore, the skin impedance as provided by COMSOL, based on experimental data (Håkansson et al., 1986), was assigned to the ear canal walls.

A normal velocity, $v_{n,ec}$, was applied to the lateral terminating surface, A_{ec} , which could be either at the entrance or the first or the second bend of the ear canal. The input

FIG. 4. Area functions of right ear canals cut at the entrance plane for IHA database subjects 1–21, and corresponding data from Rasetshwane and Neely (2011), Stinson and Lawton (1989), and Balouch et al. (2023).

FIG. 5. Mesh of the right residual ear canal for subject 5 of the IHA database cut at the entrance plane (left), at the first bend (mid), and at the second bend (right).

impedance $Z_{ec} = p_{ec}/q_{ec}$ was determined by the average sound pressure p_{ec} of all pressures p on A_{ec} divided by the volume velocity q_{ec} on A_{ec} ,

$$p_{ec} = \frac{\int p dA_{ec}}{A_{ec}}, \quad (16)$$

and

$$q_{ec} = \int v_{n,ec} dA_{ec}. \quad (17)$$

The transfer impedance $Z_{trans} = p_d/q_{ec}$ was based on p_d calculated at the umbo point. The simulation was performed for linearly distributed frequencies between 0.1 and 20 kHz, with a resolution of 100 Hz.

Sample meshes with excitation surfaces and tympanic membranes marked in blue are shown in Fig. 5. In the left column of Fig. 6, resulting levels of simulated input and transfer impedances, as well as according level differences, are shown for all 21 ear canals, each cut at the entrance, at the first bend, and at the second bend. The observed level increase towards low frequencies is characteristic for Z_{ec} , as both the ear canal and the tympanic membrane act as compliances at low frequencies. The variations of the residual ear canal lengths and shapes are reflected by shifted levels as well as shifted minima and maxima in the magnitude of Z_{ec} . The ratio of Z_{trans} to Z_{ec} is 0 dB at low frequencies, as expected for large wavelengths. This is related to the fact that the transfer parameter e_{12} is small in level at low frequencies (see the discussion in Sec. IID). Anti-resonances of Z_{ec} are canceled in Z_{trans} , whereas the frequencies of the resonances coincide.

b. Simulations using ear canal simulator and parabolic horn geometries. To reproduce the results of Rasetshwane and Neely (2011), a three-dimensional-revolved FEM simulation for the ear canal simulator introduced in Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) was carried out. For this purpose, the geometry shown in Fig. 7 at the top was taken from Fig. 2 of Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) as accurately as possible. In order to validate the one-dimensional EA model in Sec. IID with respect to three-dimensional FEM simulations, the input and transfer impedances of a simple parabolically shaped horn and a tapered variant that resembles an ear canal were also simulated (see Fig. 7, bottom). All surfaces were considered to be rigid, with no further boundary conditions except the normal velocity excitation at the larger

terminating surface, on which the input impedance Z_{ec} was determined. The transfer impedance Z_{trans} was calculated using the pressure on the center axis at 3.5 mm before the terminating surface. This choice is motivated by the observation that, on average, the projection of the umbo point on the CL for the present ear canal geometries is 3.5 mm in front of the innermost corner.

3. Measurements of input and transfer impedances

In order to validate the inverse solution with measurement data, four studies where input and transfer impedances of (residual) ear canals on human subjects were determined were considered (Blau *et al.*, 2010; Sankowsky-Rothe *et al.*, 2011; Sankowsky-Rothe *et al.*, 2015; Vogl and Blau, 2019).

FIG. 6. Level of Z_{ec} (top), Z_{trans} (middle), and Z_{trans}/Z_{ec} (bottom), derived by three-dimensional FEM simulations on 21 ear canals, each cut at the entrance and at the first and second bends, as well as on artificial, ear canal-like geometries (left column) and derived from 84 measurements on ear canals from four different databases (right column).

FIG. 7. Validation geometries: three-dimensional geometry of the ear canal simulator as used in Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) (top), a parabolic horn, and a tapered parabolic horn (bottom).

In these studies, the input sound pressure p_{mic} on which Z_{ec} was based was measured at different insertion depths, depending on the used probe. Either individual or generic ear molds, which partially had a vent, were used. In addition, the sound pressure at the eardrum p_d was measured in each of the studies, using a probe tube microphone so that the transfer impedance Z_{trans} of the ear canals could also be determined. The measurement of p_d was carried out either simultaneously with or sequentially after the measurement of the input sound pressure p_{mic} . Table I lists the most important details of the studies. Fourteen of 20 data samples had to be removed from Sankowsky-Rothe et al. (2015) due to unexpected phase curves that, according to the authors, were not correctly modeled in their post-processing [cf. Fig. 5 in Sankowsky-Rothe et al. (2015)]. The remaining samples show the typical phase shift at the first characteristic minimum of Z_{ec} (not shown here).

Measured data from all studies often show flattened Z_{ec} levels at low frequencies in comparison to simulated data. This can be explained by leakage around the impedance probe and vent effects not included in the model determining Z_{ec} from the probe measurement. This effect appeared to be particularly large in Vogl and Blau (2019), since in that study the probe tube for the simultaneous measurement of

p_d bypassed the ear mold. The level difference between transfer and input impedances at low frequencies should equal 0 dB, but it deviates in parts significantly. Also, the placement of the probe in the successive measurement of p_{mic} and p_d appeared to have introduced additional errors in measurements in Blau et al. (2010) and Sankowsky-Rothe et al. (2011). Nonetheless, most measurements are comparable to simulations. No further data entries were removed.

Measurement data in the databases have different f_{lim} values at 10, 12, or 22.05 kHz, as can be seen in Table I. Data from Blau et al. (2010) and Sankowsky-Rothe et al. (2011) are available between 0.1 kHz and 10 kHz, data from Sankowsky-Rothe et al. (2015) are available for the frequency range between 0.1 kHz and 12 kHz, and data from Vogl and Blau (2019) are available between 0 and 22.05 kHz.

B. Modified method to estimate Z_{trans}

The review in Sec. II C motivates a more thorough investigation of parameters and further adjustments of the method to obtain the inverse solution of Webster’s horn equation. The following steps of processing were finally included:

TABLE I. Details on measurement databases.

Parameter	Reference database			
	Blau et al. (2010)	Sankowsky-Rothe et al. (2011)	Sankowsky-Rothe et al. (2015)	Vogl and Blau (2019)
Number of ears (N)	$N = 10$ (cadaver ears)	$N = 20$ (pathologically normal)	$N = 6$ (without phase errors)	$N = 24$ (48 measurements for 2 ear molds)
Ear mold	Individual, closed	Individual, closed	Individual, vented, closed in 4 cases	Individual and generic, vented
Insertion depth	Beyond 2nd bend	\approx 2nd bend	Between 1st and 2nd bends (itc)	Shortly before 1st bend
Measurement p_d, p_{mic}	Successive	Successive	Quasi-simultaneous	Simultaneous
Frequency range	0.1–10 kHz	0.1–10 kHz	0.1–12 kHz	0–22.05 kHz

- (1) Extrapolation/interpolation. After determining Z_{ec} for a limited frequency range up to f_{lim} , missing values at frequencies up to $f_{sup}/2$ were extrapolated. Many methods of extrapolations were conceivable, such as a constant at zero, at a mean value across all frequencies, or at the last value at f_{lim} . We finally opted for extrapolating Z_{ec} by zero-padding, i.e., $Z_{ec} = 0$ for $f_{lim} < f < f_s/2$ (without any amplitude correction). This implied an extrapolated frequency domain reflectance to minus one.

If values at low frequencies are missing, it is also necessary to extrapolate to low frequencies. Due to the limitations of microphones and loudspeakers, this often affects frequencies below 100 Hz in measurements. In preliminary considerations, the method appeared to be robust against extrapolation of Z_{ec} to less accurate values at low frequencies. A constant at the first valid value of Z_{ec} was used in the present study.

For a subsequent interpolation of the entire frequency range (between 0 Hz and f_{sup}), the FFT length was set to ensure a frequency resolution of at least 80 Hz, with a minimum of 2^{12} .

- (2) Windowing $R(x, \omega)$. The frequency domain reflectance $R(x, \omega)$ at $x=0$ was generated by Eq. (1) with a first guess of $Z_0(x=0)$, and the Blackman window low-pass filtering was applied. Contrary to the method in Rasetshwane and Neely (2011), the cutoff frequency f_{cut} may also be above $f_s/2$, which made the previous extrapolation come into effect, since extrapolated values of the frequency domain reflectance were then not completely suppressed. Values greater than f_{cut} up to $f_{sup}/2$ were set to zero.
- (3) Adjusting the characteristic impedance and $R(x, \omega)$. The characteristic impedance at the entrance $Z_0(x=0)$, and therefore also $R(x, \omega)$, was adjusted as described in Sec. II C, based on Rasetshwane (2012a) (“surge I”) or based on Rasetshwane (2012b) (“surge II”).
- (4) Inverse solution $A(x)$ from TDR. The updated and Blackman windowed $R(x, \omega)$ at $x=0$ was transformed to the time domain (without time-reversed addition). This TDR was then used as input to calculate the inverse solution $A(x)$ of Webster’s horn equation via the finite difference approximation [as addressed in Sec. II B and taken from Rasetshwane (2012a)] up to $x = l_{max} = 50$ mm.
- (5) Transfer impedance. Finally, the inverse solution $A(0 \leq x \leq l)$ is resampled to a common spatial resolution of $\Delta x = 0.1$ mm and fed to the EA model for different lengths l , to eventually calculate Z_{trans} .

In the following, this method is referred to as the method of the present study.

IV. RESULTS

Following the reproduction of results for the ear canal simulator as utilized in Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) and the validation of the EA model, the method of the present study described in Sec. III B was *calibrated* by investigating

systematically the most advantageous parameters, so that the EA model fed by the inverse solution would provide the most accurate $Z_{trans,mod}$ compared to $Z_{trans,ref}$ obtained from three-dimensional FEM simulations. Last, the calibrated method was applied to measurements to *validate* the findings.

A. Reproduction of the inverse solution of Webster’s horn equation for an ear canal simulator

A three-dimensional FEM simulation for the ear canal simulator with $f_s = 40$ kHz, respectively, $f_{lim} = 20$ kHz, interpolated to match a FFT length of 2^{12} was carried out for the present study (see Sec. III A 2), to reproduce results of Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) by the use of MATLAB scripts provided as supplementary material (Rasetshwane, 2012a). Applying the same method, as outlined in Sec. II C, with $f_{cut} = 17$ kHz but an upsampling factor, n_s , of 3 (not 4), produced the most similar match to the true area function, shown in Fig. 8. Note that a similar underestimation of the area function as reported by Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) was observed using the measured input impedance of the ear canal simulator sampled at $f_s = 48$ kHz using an upsampling factor, n_s , of 4 [cf. Fig. 2 in Rasetshwane and Neely (2011)]. The difference between the original results (black solid line in Fig. 8) and the reproduction of present study is presumably due to small differences in the reference geometry [taken from the diagram in Fig. 2 of Rasetshwane and Neely (2011)] and to deviations between measured (Rasetshwane and Neely, 2011) and FEM simulated (present study) impedances.

For different parameter choices for f_{cut} and f_{sup} , the inverse solution varied widely. This was also the case for a modified f_s as the data could not be reproduced exactly for $f_s = 40$ kHz, demonstrating the need for careful parameter selection and the potential to obtain a more accurate area function by adjusting the parameters. The impact of the

FIG. 8. Reference geometry of the ear canal simulator and results for measured data taken from Fig. 2 in Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) and results applying the method by Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) [conforming with Rasetshwane (2012a)] and the modified method by Rasetshwane (2012b) to three-dimensional FEM simulated data for the ear canal simulator (calculated area functions ending at l_{TDR50} for $f_s=40$ kHz, $f_{cut} = 17$ kHz, and n_s values of 3 and 4, where $f_{lim} = f_s/2, f_{sup} = n_s \cdot f_s$).

divergent approaches in Rasetshwane (2012a) compared to Rasetshwane (2012b) is further illustrated in Fig. 8 for the case of the ear canal simulator calculated for $n_s = 3$ and $f_{\text{cut}} = 17$ kHz. The effect of the time-reversed addition [removed in Rasetshwane (2012b)] appeared negligible. The algorithms “surge I” and “surge II” adjusting $Z_0(x = 0)$ yielded similar results. On the other hand, the amplitude correction [also removed in Rasetshwane (2012b)] changed the inverse solution considerably.

B. Validation of the EA model

For validation purposes, $Z_{\text{trans,ref}}$ was determined for the parabolic horns shown in the lower illustration of Fig. 7. The known area functions with spatial resolutions Δx of 1 mm and 0.1 mm were fed into the EA model, as described in Sec. II D, to calculate transfer impedances $Z_{\text{trans,mod}}$. Fig. 9 shows the level and the phase of the error between one-dimensional and three-dimensional simulations. The mean of the root-mean-square (rms) level and phase errors, L_{rmse} and ϑ_{rmse} , calculated by

$$L_{\text{rmse}} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{f=1}^{10\text{kHz}} \left(20 \lg \left(\left| \frac{Z_{\text{trans,mod}}}{Z_{\text{trans,ref}}} \right| \right) \right)^2}{n_f}} \text{ dB} \quad (18)$$

and

$$\vartheta_{\text{rmse}} = \sqrt{\frac{\sum_{f=1}^{10\text{kHz}} \left(\arg \left(\frac{Z_{\text{trans,mod}}}{Z_{\text{trans,ref}}} \right) \right)^2}{n_f}} \cdot \frac{180^\circ}{\pi}, \quad (19)$$

with n_f being the number of frequencies included in the frequency range between 1 and 10 kHz and distributed linearly in steps of 100 Hz, are also shown. This frequency range was chosen since the context of the present work pertains to speech applications up to 10 kHz and since Z_{trans} equals Z_{ec} below 1 kHz, as described in Sec. II D. Level errors did not

FIG. 9. Validation of one-dimensional EA model: level and phase differences between transfer impedances calculated by one-dimensional EA model re-simulated by three-dimensional FEM model for the two horns shown at the bottom of Fig. 7, using a spatial resolution Δx of 0.1 mm; the frequency range of interest (1–10 kHz) is shaded blue.

exceed ± 0.06 dB between 1 and 10 kHz, with a mean rms level error of 0.04 dB. The absolute phase error was below 0.11° between 1 and 10 kHz, with a mean rms phase error of 0.04° . For $\Delta x = 1$ mm, level errors increased up to ± 0.5 dB, with a mean rms level error of 0.23 dB. The absolute phase error was below 0.15° , with a mean rms phase error of 0.04° .

A resolution of 0.1 mm can be considered to be sufficiently accurate and is used in the following.

C. Method calibration

1. Transfer impedance error as a function of the termination length of the inverse solution

At the top of Fig. 10, the inverse solution is shown for one exemplary ear canal cut at the first bend. Also, shown are the reference area function known from extraction with the vmtk toolbox, and different lengths to be introduced in Sec. IV C 2. The optimal length for the inverse solution at which the resulting transfer impedance error is minimal is of interest. For an inverse solution calculated to a maximum length, l_{max} , each x in $0 < x \leq l_{\text{max}}$ was considered to be a possible termination length of the inverse solution. All these possible solutions were passed to the one-dimensional EA model to calculate $Z_{\text{trans,mod}}$ for each step. Then, each $Z_{\text{trans,mod}}$ was compared to the simulated reference $Z_{\text{trans,ref}}$ so that L_{rmse} [Eq. (18)] and ϑ_{rmse} [Eq. (19)] for frequencies f between 1 kHz and 10 kHz could be determined for each iteration as a function of x , shown at the bottom of Fig. 10. The length at the least mean level error of the transfer

FIG. 10. Exemplary data of the inverse solution for one ear cut at the entrance plane. From top to bottom are shown the estimated $A_{\text{inv.sol.}}(x)$ and reference $A_{\text{ref}}(x)$ area functions, gradient of the logarithmic area function $\epsilon(x)$ of the inverse solution, time domain reflectance [TDR (x)], and mean (across frequency) rms errors of the transfer impedance level [Eq. (18)] and phase [Eq. (19)]. In the bottom diagram, the optimal termination length l_{ime} defined at the minimum of $L_{\text{rmse}}(x)$ is also shown. The definitions of the other lengths are given in Sec. IV C 5.

impedance associated with the global minimum of $L_{\text{rmse}}(x)$ is termed l_{lme} . l_{lme} is an intermediate variable that can only be determined using reference data and is not known in the use case. In the following, it will serve as a basis for determining the optimal parameters that can then be used for the use case without any reference data. Note that the length associated with the least mean level error L_{lme} does not necessarily coincide with that of the least mean phase error ϑ_{lme} . However, the mean phase error $\vartheta_{\text{rmse}}(x)$ is reasonably small over a wide range of x . Therefore, the length associated with the least mean level error L_{lme} is regarded as the optimal termination length and used in the following.

2. Reflectance upsampling for a sufficient spatial resolution

Keeping f_{lim} constant at 20 kHz for different values of $f_{\text{cut}} = [8, 9, \dots, 44]$ kHz and $f_{\text{sup}} = [0.02, 0.04, \dots, 0.12, 0.125, 0.144, 0.16, 0.192, 0.25, 0.5, \dots, 2, 2.5, \dots, 5, 7.5, 10]$ MHz, the least mean level errors L_{lme} and phase errors ϑ_{lme} were determined for all 21 ear canal geometries cut at three different lengths, for each combination of f_{cut} and f_{sup} , employing the method of the present study (with “surge I”). The mean of all 21 L_{lme} and ϑ_{lme} values for one group of cut planes is shown as the L_{mlme} and ϑ_{mlme} in Fig. 11. One can observe that L_{mlme} values decrease for medium and higher f_{sup} . A saturation effect can be observed with only minor improvement above $f_{\text{sup}} = 3.5$ MHz. Above $f_{\text{sup}} = 3.5$ MHz, a L_{mlme} of < 0.6 dB is reached for f_{cut} between 20 kHz and 35 kHz for all three groups of cut planes. The shorter the ear canals, the smaller the minimal L_{mlme} . The mean phase error ϑ_{mlme} slightly increases in the field of lowest level errors (visible for group

FIG. 11. Dependency of the mean value of L_{lme} across all 21 ears (L_{mlme}) and of the mean value of ϑ_{lme} across all 21 ears (ϑ_{mlme}) on f_{sup} and f_{cut} for ear canals cut at the entrance and first and second bends (from top to bottom) at $f_{\text{lim}} = 20$ kHz.

“bend 2”), but is still limited to less than 2° . In the following, $f_{\text{sup}} = 3.5$ MHz is considered as a sufficiently high spatial resolution, with $\Delta x \approx 0.1$ mm for $c = 351.8$ m/s (for a temperature in the ear canal of $T = 308$ °K).

3. Adjustment of $Z_0(x = 0)$

In Sec. II C, two approaches (“surge I” and “surge II”) were presented for adjusting the characteristic impedance. A small difference between these two approaches was observed in the resulting area functions for the ear canal simulator in Sec. IV A. In order to analyze the resulting accuracy of transfer impedance predictions, the least mean level error L_{lme} was determined for all 21 ear canal geometries cut at the three different lengths, using $f_{\text{lim}} = 20$ kHz and $f_{\text{sup}} = 3.5$ MHz, at different values for $f_{\text{cut}} = [8, 9, \dots, 44]$ kHz. The mean of all L_{lme} values L_{mlme} is again used as an error indicator and is shown as a function of f_{cut} in Fig. 12. Given the availability of a geometric reference, a third method utilizes the actual value of $A(x = 0)$ in Eq. (2) to determine $Z_0(x = 0)$. As can be seen in Fig. 12, the optimal performance can be achieved utilizing “surge I” at $f_{\text{cut}} = 28$ kHz.

4. Linear model for optimal f_{cut} re f_{lim}

Based on the results from Secs. IVC2 and IVC3, “surge I” is applied and f_{sup} is kept constant at 3.5 MHz in the following. The dependency of L_{mlme} and ϑ_{mlme} on the parameters f_{lim} and f_{cut} is shown in Fig. 13, separately for the groups of cut planes. The higher the f_{lim} , the wider the interval of advantageous f_{cut} . ϑ_{mlme} essentially does not exceed 2° , where L_{mlme} is small and is therefore not considered in the following.

In Fig. 14, values of f_{cut} at minimum L_{mlme} are shown as a function of f_{lim} . From these data, one linear regression model for the best value for f_{cut} for a given value of f_{lim} was estimated.

To assess the robustness and generalizability of this linear regression model, a repeated cross-validation approach was employed (Hastie et al., 2009). Instead of modeling each condition separately, the analysis focused on the average response across all three conditions, aiming to capture a general trend while enhancing model stability. In each of 1000 cross-validation iterations, ear canals from 10 subjects

FIG. 12. Dependency of L_{mlme} on f_{cut} for different methods, adjusting the characteristic impedance for all ear canals with $f_{\text{lim}} = 20$ kHz and $f_{\text{sup}} = 3.5$ MHz.

FIG. 13. Dependency of the mean value of L_{mlme} across all 21 ears (L_{mlme}) and of the mean value of θ_{mlme} across all 21 ears (θ_{mlme}) on f_{lim} and f_{cut} for ear canals cut at the entrance and first and second bends (from top to bottom) at $f_{sup} = 3.5$ MHz.

were randomly selected for model training, and the remaining 11 were excluded from all three groups of ear canal lengths and served as a test set. For both training and test subsets, group mean values were determined for each f_{lim} value. A linear regression model was then fitted to the training group mean values. The resulting model parameters—slope and intercept—were applied to the test mean values. The prediction accuracy was quantified using the error difference between predicted and actual test values. As shown in Fig. 15, the validation demonstrated a strong consistency between training and testing distributions for the slope and the intercept. The mean group difference between $f_{cut,train}$ and $f_{cut,test}$ is close to 0 kHz, with a standard deviation of less than 0.7 kHz. These results indicate that the linear relationship is stable across subsamples and conditions, with limited variability in model parameters and moderate prediction error.

FIG. 14. Linear regression model for the relation between f_{lim} and f_{cut} at minima of L_{mlme} , extracted from data shown in Fig. 13.

FIG. 15. Distributions of the estimated slopes, intercepts, and the mean group error differences between tested and trained f_{cut} from repeated cross-validation (1000 iterations, train/test split of 10/11 ear canals cut at three different lengths).

The final model used in the following was fitted to the group means for all 21 ear canals cut at the three different lengths, achieving a R^2 of 83%, with

$$f_{cut} = 1.0545 \cdot f_{lim} + 6.8788 \text{ kHz.} \quad (20)$$

With this regression model, an optimal f_{cut} of 28 kHz is obtained for $f_{lim} = 20$ kHz. Together with $f_{sup} = 3.5$ MHz and “surge I”, the inverse solution of Webster’s horn equation results in the area functions shown in Fig. 16 as “present study.” They can be seen to agree well with the reference area functions, with the exception of a slight underestimation, especially at the lateral end, as shown in Fig. 16 for ear

FIG. 16. Reference area functions of ear canals cut at entrance plane vs inverse solutions, as calculated in the present study, for $f_{sup} = 3.5$ MHz, $f_{lim} = 20$ kHz, and $f_{cut} = 28$ kHz up to $x = 50$ mm.

canals cut at the entrance. Also, using the same parameter choice for the ear canal simulator yields an inverse solution that better matches the true geometry, compared to the best possible match reached with the method reported in Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) and implemented in Rasetshwane (2012a) (see Fig. 17 in this study).

5. Termination length of the inverse solution

For an optimal estimation of the transfer impedance, the inverse solution needs to be limited at l_{lme} (introduced in Sec. IV C 1). This value is not known in the application case. In the following, different termination lengths are examined. Figure 10 shows some lengths that are known from the geometric ear canal models or can be derived from inverse solutions. First, there is the geometric length l_{geoend} , defined between the lateral end of the ear canal and the innermost point of the CL. Second, the length l_{umbo} between the lateral end of the ear canal and the umbo point, projected on the CL, may be of interest. Furthermore, the maximum of the TDR can be used to infer a length, l_{TDRmax} , which is related to the reflection at the eardrum. In Rasetshwane (2012b), the end of the ear canal is associated with l_{TDR50} where the TDR has decayed to 50% of its maximum. The global minimum of the gradient of the logarithmic area function ϵ at the length l_ϵ also appears to be prominent.

The distributions of these termination lengths of the inverse solutions (calculated using $f_{lim} = 20$ kHz, $f_{sup} = 3.5$ MHz, and $f_{cut} = 28$ kHz) determined for all ear canal geometries are shown in the top diagram of Fig. 18. In addition, the quarter-wavelength, $l_{quarter}$, derived from the frequency of the first characteristic minimum of the Z_{ec} , is also shown. Characteristic length differences are shown in the middle and bottom diagrams of Fig. 18.

The interquartile range of the absolute length l_{geoend} of the ear canals cut at the entrance is approximately 30–35 mm, and the interquartile ranges are 26–29 mm and 19–21 mm for ear canal geometries cut at the first and second bends, respectively. The median distance between l_{umbo} and l_{geoend} is observed to be between 3 and 4 mm. The

FIG. 17. Exact area function of the ear canal simulator and inverse solutions up to $x = l_{TDR50}$, applying the method of Rasetshwane and Neely (2011), for $f_{sup} = 120$ kHz, $f_{lim} = 20$ kHz, and $f_{cut} = 17$ kHz and the method modified in present study for $f_{sup} = 3.5$ MHz, $f_{lim} = 20$ kHz, and $f_{cut} = 28$ kHz.

FIG. 18. Absolute termination lengths (top) and length differences (middle and bottom) from inverse solutions calculated by setting $f_{sup} = 3.5$ MHz, $f_{lim} = 20$ kHz, and $f_{cut} = 28$ kHz.

median lengths of l_ϵ and l_{TDRmax} lie between the medians of l_{umbo} and l_{geoend} , with the median l_ϵ somewhat closer to the end. The median of l_{TDR50} is about 1 to 2.5 mm behind the geometric end. The quarter wave lengths are largely scattered and much shorter than the median of the length l_{geoend} .

For further investigation, the difference between the lengths l_{TDR50} , l_{TDRmax} , and l_ϵ obtained from the inverse solution and the location of the least mean error l_{lme} is of particular importance. The medians of these differences are all positive, indicating that the termination length tends to be overestimated. The scatter is approximately the same for all lengths.

The effect of using different termination lengths on the resulting accuracy of transfer impedance predictions is shown in Fig. 19, together with the accuracy of the original method by Rasetshwane and Neely (2011). Values for L_{rmse} and ϑ_{rmse} were determined for all ear canal geometries. Feeding the one-dimensional EA model with the vmtk-derived area function limited at the projected umbo point provides the best performance in terms of the median of L_{rmse} in comparison to the three-dimensional simulation. Using the inverse solution terminated at l_{lme} achieved slightly larger median values of less than 0.6 dB and 2°. The termination at l_{TDR50} degraded the performance more than a termination at l_{TDRmax} or l_ϵ , as expected, caused by the larger distance between l_{lme} and l_{TDRmax} .

FIG. 19. Boxplot showing values for L_{rmse} (top) and ϑ_{rmse} (bottom), calculated for simulation-based data, using the vmtk-derived area function, applying the method by Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) as implemented in Rasetshwane (2012a), with an optimal n_s of 3 and $f_{cut} = 17$ kHz for $f_{lim} = 20$ kHz, as well as applying the method of the present study at $f_{sup} = 3.5$ MHz, $f_{lim} = 20$ kHz, and $f_{cut} = 28$ kHz.

It was hypothesized that the termination of the inverse solution at distance-corrected lengths would provide a more accurate prediction of Z_{trans} . The values for this length correction equal the median differences of l_{TDR50} , l_{TDRmax} , and l_{ϵ} to l_{lme} , derived from data of all three groups shown at the bottom of Fig. 18. With length corrections for l_{ϵ} by 1.8 mm and l_{TDRmax} by 0.9 mm, there seems to be a small improvement for L_{rmse} and a prominent improvement for the corrected lengths at $l_{TDR50} - 4.3$ mm, compared to the respective non-corrected lengths, and a general reasonable improvement concerning ϑ_{rmse} . Errors for terminating the inverse solution at corrected length produce similar scattering. Smaller median L_{rmse} can be achieved for shorter ear canals. The median L_{rmse} for the termination at corrected lengths is ≈ 0.15 dB above the value reached with a termination at l_{lme} . Terminating the inverse solution at $x = l_{\epsilon} - 1.8$ mm yielded visually the best results. The results of the original method by Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) could thus be noticeably improved, in particular for longer ear canals.

A closer examination of the frequency response of the error obtained for the inverse solution terminated at l_{lme} with $f_{sup} = 3.5$ MHz, $f_{lim} = 20$ kHz, and $f_{cut} = 28$ kHz reveals

that the resonances are accurately captured, since this information is given by Z_{cc} , but the magnitude of Z_{trans} below and between the resonances deviates, resulting in a wavy frequency dependency of the error, as shown in Fig. 20. In addition, the errors increase above 10 kHz, as expected.

D. Validation using measured input and transfer impedances

1. Application of the linear model for the selection of f_{cut} for a given f_{lim}

For a given f_{lim} of the measurements from Blau *et al.* (2010), Sankowsky-Rothe *et al.* (2011), Sankowsky-Rothe *et al.* (2015), and Vogl and Blau (2019), presented in

FIG. 20. Transfer impedance errors and 10th and 90th percentiles (with respect to the three-dimensional FEM simulation), for ear canal geometries cut at the entrance (top), at the first bend (middle) and the second bend (bottom): $Z_{trans,mod}$ was calculated by the inverse solution (with $f_{sup} = 3.5$ MHz, $f_{lim} = 20$ kHz, and $f_{cut} = 28$ kHz; “surge I”), terminated at l_{lme} , and fed into the one-dimensional EA model; the frequency range of interest (1–10 kHz) is shaded blue.

Sec. III A 3, optimal f_{cut} values at 17.4, 17.4, 19.5, and 30.1 kHz (rounded to the first decimal) were determined using the linear model from Eq. (20). In addition, values for L_{mlme} and ϑ_{mlme} were computed as a function of f_{cut} for $f_{\text{sup}} = 3.5$ MHz and applying “surge I.” This analysis was limited to presumed length intervals, since otherwise, l_{lme} and other termination lengths were occasionally unrealistically short or long. For example, $L_{\text{rmse}}(x)$ showed further local minima at multiples of the ear canal length for the selected frequency range of 1–10 kHz (see Fig. 10, bottom). The limits were chosen based on a length analysis for the 21 ear canal geometries shown in Fig. 18 (top), yielding the following conservative assumptions: (1) The length between entrance and umbo point does not exceed 45 mm, (2) the length between first bend and umbo point is in the interval [15, 35] mm, and (3) the length between the second bend and umbo point is in the interval [10, 25] mm. Together with the insertion depths reported by the authors of the studies containing the experimental data, conservative limits of residual ear canal lengths were derived for the given insertion depths (see Table II).

Predictions for f_{cut} of the linear model were then compared to actual optimal values for f_{cut} at global minima of L_{mlme} . As for simulation-based data (see Fig. 13), a valley also forms for the measurements. Therefore, the model value of f_{cut} and the best possible value at the minimum can lie some distance apart without adding a major error. In fact, the additional error between the minimal possible L_{mlme} and the value at f_{cut} derived by the linear model is less than 0.17 dB for all databases (see Fig. 21).

2. Application of termination criteria to measurements

In the presumed limitation intervals, with $f_{\text{sup}} = 3.5$ MHz and f_{cut} selected using the linear model from Eq. (20), derived termination lengths are shown in Fig. 22. Regarding termination length corrections, the length differences between $l_{\text{TDR}50}$, l_{ϵ} or l_{TDRmax} , and l_{lme} reproduced the tendency of length overestimations that was already observed for simulation-based data in Sec. IV C 5, in the same order. The length differences for measured data scatter more widely. The TDR decayed less quickly compared to simulation results. For a total of four measurements across three databases, no $l_{\text{TDR}50}$ could be

TABLE II. Insertion depths and derived length intervals for the experimental data used for validation. Note that Blau *et al.* (2010) also reported residual ear canal lengths (from the inner face of the ear mold—beyond the second bend—to the innermost point of the ear canal) between 10.8 mm and 15 mm.

Reference database	Insertion depth	[min, max] length of residual ear canal (mm)
Blau <i>et al.</i> (2010)	Beyond 2nd bend	[3, 20]
Sankowsky-Rothe <i>et al.</i> (2011)	2nd bend	[5, 30]
Sankowsky-Rothe <i>et al.</i> (2015)	itc (between 1st and 2nd bends)	[10, 35]
Vogl and Blau (2019)	Before 1st bend	[15, 45]

FIG. 21. Analysis of resulting mean least mean transfer impedance level errors for measurement databases: dependency of L_{mlme} on f_{cut} for $f_{\text{sup}} = 3.5$ MHz. Also shown are f_{cut} predicted from f_{lim} using the model of Eq. (20) (crosses) and global minima of the respective measurements (circles).

identified within the presumed length interval, as indicated by the reduced sample number n^* above the respective boxes.

Figure 23 shows values of L_{rmse} and ϑ_{rmse} derived with different termination lengths for the measurements. The median of the least mean error for three databases was slightly below 2 dB, and that for one database was below 3 dB. Concerning the phase, the median of the least mean error was below 20° . With an additional level error between 0.5 and 0.8 dB and no additional phase error, the corrected and the non-corrected termination lengths l_{ϵ} and l_{TDRmax} achieved a similar accuracy and appear to be suitable for accurate predictions. The interquartile range increased slightly compared to the simulation results.

Regarding the original method of Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) as implemented in Rasetshwane (2012a), a comparison is only meaningful for the data of Vogl and Blau (2019), since the value of f_{lim} for this database is similar to the value used in the calibration and larger than the optimal f_{cut} of 17 kHz for this method. Compared to results

FIG. 22. Results on measurements showing absolute lengths (top) and length differences (bottom), derived at $f_{\text{sup}} = 3.5$ MHz, f_{lim} given by the respective database, and optimal f_{cut} taken from the linear regression model [Eq. (20)].

FIG. 23. Validation results on measurements showing L_{rmse} (top) and ϑ_{rmse} (bottom) for the method by Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) and for the optimized method employed in the present study, with $f_{sup} = 3.5$ MHz, f_{lim} given by database, and optimal f_{cut} taken from the linear regression model from Eq. (20).

derived by the modified method employed in the present study, the accuracy of the original method is substantially lower, in particular for the level (see Fig. 23).

Finally, the frequency-dependent errors of transfer impedance predictions are shown in Fig. 24 for each database. Considering measurement uncertainties, the authors defined a tolerance range of ± 5 dB and $\pm 20^\circ$ in the frequency interval $1\text{ kHz} \leq f \leq 10\text{ kHz}$ for these databases in their respective publications. These tolerance ranges were only slightly exceeded for the present study with regard to the 10th and 90th percentiles.

As suggested by Vogl and Blau (2019) for their measurements, contributions of higher frequencies in Z_{ec} were suppressed by reducing f_{lim} to 10 kHz, and the predictions of the transfer impedances for this database utilizing the method of the present study were repeated with an appropriately adjusted f_{cut} of 17.4 kHz. However, as a result, the accuracy decreased, with a mean L_{rmse} of 4.77 dB and a mean ϑ_{rmse} of 23.65° .

V. DISCUSSION

Utilizing the method of the present study with optimal, or re-calibrated, parameters on data obtained from

FIG. 24. Transfer impedance errors and 10th and 90th percentiles with respect to the measurements from Blau *et al.* (2010), Sankowsky-Rothe *et al.* (2011), Sankowsky-Rothe *et al.* (2015), and Vogl and Blau (2019) (from top to bottom): $Z_{trans,mod}$ was calculated by the inverse solution (with $f_{sup} = 3.5$ MHz, database-specific $f_{lim} = [10, 10, 12, 22.05]$ kHz, and $f_{cut} = [17.4, 17.4, 19.5, 30.1]$ kHz; “surge I”), terminated at $l_{e-1.8mm}$, and fed into the one-dimensional EA model; the frequency range of interest (1–10 kHz) is shaded blue, and the tolerance range is shaded green.

three-dimensional FEM simulations for human ear canals and an ear canal simulator, the accuracy of the predicted ear canal area functions improves considerably in comparison to the method from Rasetshwane and Neely (2011).

Nevertheless, a number of causes may impede the precision of the predicted area function.

First, ear canals essentially resemble parabolically curved truncated cones, with frequent tapering at the first bend. The cross-sections of real ear canals are elliptical rather than circular. However, the good agreement of the transfer impedance from the three-dimensional FEM simulation and that from the one-dimensional EA model fed with the vmtk area function of the ear canals imply that the neglected curvature of the CL and the actual elliptical shape of the ear canal cross-sections probably contribute less to the error, including frequencies between 1 kHz and 10 kHz (cf. L_{rmse} and θ_{rmse} for “ref. geometry” in Fig. 19). A tendency to underestimate the area function still remains, especially at the lateral end of the ear canal and in regions of strongly varying area functions.

Second, the remaining underestimation of the area function might be due to incorrect assumptions about the sound field, which limit the range of validity of the theoretical calculations. For parabolic horn geometries with a perfect straight CL and perfect circular cross-sections, the area functions show a similar underestimation to that seen for ear canal geometries, as could also be seen in Rasetshwane *et al.* (2012) for the parabolic horn. An examination of the result for the ear canal simulator (Fig. 17, violet line) indicates that, with a more accurate estimate for $A(x=0)$, i.e., after adjusting $Z_0(x=0)$, $A(x)$ would also be less underestimated in regions of strongly varying area functions.

Two different methods for adjusting the characteristic impedance $Z_0(x=0)$, namely, the one given by Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) [conforming with Rasetshwane (2012a), “surge I”] and the one given in Rasetshwane (2012b) (“surge II”), were investigated. At the lateral end, the underestimation of $A(x=0)$ for ear canals appeared to vanish using the second method. On the other hand, the fitting resulting from the first method is preferable and even more suitable than the calculation of Z_0 according to Eq. (2) with the known geometric reference area. Dispersion and non-planar wave propagation, as well as strong changes in the area function, likely contribute to the error. As mentioned in Sec. I, an approach to determine a more accurate TDR for real ear canals can be found in Nørgaard *et al.* (2019) and Keefe (2020).

Third, the inverse solution of Webster’s horn equation is performed without additional boundary conditions at the eardrum, i.e., by assuming a rigid termination. Also, rigid ear canal walls and lossless sound propagation are implied. This discrepancy between the simulated or measured input data and the model should also lead to an error that is not precisely quantified here. This phenomenon may be most apparent within the mid-frequency range around the minimum of the eardrum impedance level. Above 3 kHz, the eardrum can be approximated as a rigid boundary (Hudde *et al.*, 1999). In Wulbusch *et al.* (2023), the eardrum impedance, coupled to a residual volume according to Hudde and Engel (1998) and Hudde *et al.* (1999), is assumed as a boundary condition at a length l , which is determined in the

fitting process. The present study’s methodology does not provide a fitting of this manner.

Last, the continuation of the input impedance spectrum, accompanied by the continuation of the reflectance spectrum, was found to be important in order to achieve an adequate spatial sampling through a high value of f_{sup} , whereby the error can still be reduced to a relevant extent with a sampling Δx of 0.1 mm, according to Xia *et al.* (2024). Alternative approaches to model ear canal acoustics, i.e., Sankowsky-Rothe *et al.* (2011), Sankowsky-Rothe *et al.* (2015), and Keefe *et al.* (2025), may also benefit from a finer spatial resolution. However, instead of extrapolating Z_{ec} to high frequencies (up to $f_{\text{sup}}/2$) with a constant value, as proposed in the present work, there may be more suitable methods. A continuation of the input impedance spectrum predicted from lower frequencies ($< f_s/2$) utilizing potential periodic properties of (non)harmonic frequency components given by (non)integer frequency ratios of resonances and antiresonances might be conceivable, as this would prevent the need for windowing.

The optimal ratio of f_{cut} to f_{lim} was examined using three-dimensional simulations for one sample of 21 ear canal geometries for three different lengths. Higher values of f_{lim} are recommended in order to increase the bandwidth of a favorable f_{cut} where the error rate is low (Fig. 13): For higher f_{lim} , the method is more robust against a possibly non-optimal f_{cut} selection for other samples. In addition, it has been shown that the linear relationship is stable across subsamples and conditions, with limited variability in model parameters and moderate prediction error. Furthermore, the additional error is not substantial for measurements of four different independent samples.

In the following, the suitability of the different lengths for the termination of the inverse solution for an optimal estimation of the transfer impedance is addressed.

The median distance between the umbo point (projected on the CL) at l_{umbo} and the geometric ear canal end at l_{geoend} is 3.5 mm, which is close to Hudde’s assumption of a cone-like residual volume with a cone length of 4 mm (Hudde and Engel, 1998). The umbo point was used by Rasetshwane and Neely (2011) as reflection point and is approximately given by the distance corresponding to the time at which the TDR reaches its maximum. l_{TDRmax} only slightly overestimates the reference umbo length in geometric ear canal models (mostly less than 2 mm). The geometric end of the entire ear canal at l_{geoend} was associated with l_{TDR50} by Rasetshwane (2012b), which turned out to overestimate the geometric ear canal length to the same minor extent.

Regarding the termination of the inverse solution at l_{ime} for the most accurate prediction of Z_{trans} , l_{ime} was found to coincide quite well with l_{umbo} , with deviations of less than 1 mm in most cases. Since l_{ime} is unknown in the use case, the present study investigated a length criterion extractable from the available data. In addition to the termination criteria of mentioned lengths l_{TDRmax} and l_{TDR50} , the global minimum of ϵ derived from the inverse solution at l_{ϵ} , which reliably occurred between the projected umbo point and the

innermost corner, was proposed. With length corrections that moved termination criteria closer to the length of the least mean error, small improvements for the level and considerable improvements for the predicted phase of Z_{trans} could be achieved in reference to simulated data for ear canal geometries. A termination of the inverse solution at $x = l_e - 1.8 \text{ mm}$ or $x = l_{\text{TDRmax}} - 0.9 \text{ mm}$ turned out to yield the most accurate Z_{trans} for the three-dimensional FEM simulation.

However, regarding the validation results on measurements, the advantage of the length correction disappeared, presumably because correction lengths of 0.9 mm and 1.8 mm are smaller than the positioning accuracy of the probe tube at the eardrum, addressing the problem of an inaccurate reference.

Further aspects need to be considered with regard to the measurements. Especially in the database of [Vogl and Blau \(2019\)](#), it is frequently observed that the levels of Z_{trans} given in the database are lower than levels of corresponding Z_{cc} , a phenomenon that did not occur in the simulations. Therefore, a bias to positive level errors around 4–6 kHz was expected but did not occur for the data from [Vogl and Blau \(2019\)](#). Conversely, a tendency to negative errors around 2.5 kHz (slightly above the first, strongly flattened anti-resonance in Z_{cc}) can presumably be explained by particularly unfavorable geometries, as the input impedance is not determined at the residual ear canal, but in the vent of the ear mold. Thus, part of the ear mold had to be accommodated by the area function, with a cross-sectional jump at the entrance to the residual ear canal, violating the assumptions of Webster’s horn equation.

Contrary to expectations, reducing f_{lim} to 10 kHz and f_{cut} to 17.4 kHz for this database in order to weaken potentially non-valid contributions of higher frequencies in the reflectance decreased the prediction accuracy for Z_{trans} , confirming the benefit of higher f_{lim} .

Generally, transfer impedance errors resulting from application of the (optimized) method of the present study did not exceed tolerance limits, as defined in related publications between 1 and 10 kHz, or can be attributed to measurement inaccuracies, as addressed in [Sec. III A 3](#). Below 1 kHz, errors were larger, but also less relevant, as the desired transfer impedance equals the known input impedance at these frequencies. Reported errors in related publications of the databases from [Blau et al. \(2010\)](#), [Sankowsky-Rothe et al. \(2011\)](#), and [Sankowsky-Rothe et al. \(2015\)](#) are only slightly smaller. For the database from [Vogl and Blau \(2019\)](#), the method presented there achieves smaller level errors, in particular in the medium frequency range. For a thorough investigation, a systematic comparison of all methods to predict Z_{trans} is necessary.

VI. CONCLUSION

Predictions of ear canal area functions from measured input impedances can be substantially improved by increasing the upsampling frequency to 3.5 MHz, corresponding to

0.1 mm spatial resolution at the Courant–Friedrichs–Lewy limit, by increasing the frequency range of the input impedance of the residual ear canal and by adjusting the cutoff frequency of the Blackman window, depending on the highest frequency of the input impedance using the linear regression model as presented. Slight and systematic underestimations remain for parabolic shapes, probably due to the limitations of Webster’s horn equation. For a sufficiently high spatial resolution, the global minimum of the gradient of the logarithmic inverse solution ϵ and the maximum of the time domain reflectance are both good predictors of the ear canal length. For the purpose of individual equalization of the eardrum sound pressure, the method can be supplemented by a one-dimensional EA model capable of predicting the transfer impedance of the ear canal. An equalization based on the method of the present study presumably outperforms non-individualized equalization algorithms, but it needs to be compared to other methods.

The advantage of the method, despite slight underestimates of the area functions, is its reproducibility and robustness with consistently plausible results for a wide range of insertion depths. Finally, the computational load is very low compared to non-linear fitting algorithms. The inverse solution could be employed to initialize and constrain parameters of other fitting algorithms making them more robust.

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AUTHOR DECLARATIONS

Conflict of Interest

The authors have no conflicts to disclose.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The data that support the findings of this study are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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